

COMELD™ JOINTS: A NOVEL TECHNIQUE FOR BONDING COMPOSITES AND METAL

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SUMMARY

Design solutions using composite laminates frequently require joining the laminates to metal. A novel approach to such bonding using a sculpted metal surface has been proposed; this approach can be described as a combination of mechanical and adhesive bonding. This paper describes the optimisation of the geometry of the sculpted metal surface.

Keywords: Comeld™ Joint, protrusion geometry, protrusion density, bonding, finite element analysis

INTRODUCTION

Composite materials are slowly gaining acceptance as structural materials particularly in applications when weight saving is a critical consideration. However, in general, the uptake in structural applications for composites during the last decade has been disappointingly slow. In many large-scale applications, a total composite solution may be unrealistic; composites must be joined to metals. Reliable use of composite materials therefore relies on reliable joining technologies. The development of good joining methods between metals and composites may be described as a pre-requisite for increased applications for composites.

There is an intrinsic dilemma for the design of composite joints, since the two alternatives of mechanical or adhesive bonding both show significant disadvantages [e.g 1-2]. The most promising way forward may be a combination of adhesive and mechanical bonding. This combination of joining methods may now be attained following the development of Surfi-Sculpt® technology by TWI. This technology uses a power electron beam to create various surface textures through the manipulation of the electron beam. This technique is applicable to a wide range of materials, allowing the creation of a range of hole and patterns, which can be precisely controlled.

Bonding of the sculpted metal surface to composite laminates forms a Comeld™ joint. Various joint geometries could be manufactured using this technology; we have chosen a double-lap joint stressed in tension as a reasonable analogue of typical joints between composites and metals. This paper describes the optimisation, using finite element simulations, of the geometry of the protrusions: shape, angle and density.

JOINT GEOMETRY

The optimisation presented here is for a two-step joint double-lap joint in quasi-static tension; the geometry of the joint is shown in Figure 1. The total length of the joint is 150 mm, width 25 mm, and the total thickness is 3 mm. The height of both steps is 1 mm.

Figure 1 Geometry of the Joint

The metal adherends are Titanium Ti-6Al-4V and the composite is carbon fibre prepreg AS4/8552 from Hexcel. The laminate lay-up was $[0/90]_{4s}$, with ply thickness of approximately 0.125mm. The material properties for the Titanium and the unidirectional CFRP were gained from the literature [3].

There are many variables to be investigated, which cannot all be investigated simultaneously. These analyses have been carried out for a given height and volume of each protrusion. The variables investigated have been the shape, angle and density of the protrusions. The height and diameter of the protrusions were gained from experimental measurements and remained constant: height 1mm, diameter 0.6mm. All results presented in this paper have been gained assuming a square array of protrusions. The measured density of the protrusions, D , was 0.54 per mm^2 .

Initial analyses were carried out for the symmetric shape protrusion, as shown in Figure 2a; this is the 'parallel shape' protrusion. Both edges remain parallel to each other for all protrusion angles. However, careful inspection of the micrographs (see Figure 1) showed that the shape of the protrusions was not symmetric; this shape has been idealised using the geometry shown in Figure 2b; this is the 'hill shape' protrusion. For the hill shaped protrusion one edge remains vertical for all protrusion angles while the opposite edge is oriented at the protrusion angle. The angled edge is the edge closest to the composite end of the joint. Analyses have been carried out for different orientations of the protrusions. The definition of the angle is with respect to the vertical protrusion as shown in Figure 2c; for the parallel shape protrusion, the angle α is defined with respect to the edges of the protrusion and the vertical direction; for the hill shape protrusion the

Figure 2 Idealised Geometry of Protrusion Shape a) Parallel shape b) Hill Shape
c) Definition of Angle

angle β is defined between the angled edge and the vertical. The angle defined as positive means that the protrusion leans towards the composite end of the joint. The perpendicular protrusion at 0° is the same shape for both shapes of protrusion.

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

The overall aim of the simulations is to examine the stress distributions around individual protrusions arising from the tensile loading of the joint. The mesh required to examine such stress distributions is fine and could not be achieved for a model of the entire joint geometry. A multi-scale modelling approach is required.

To simulate an individual protrusion, a unit cell approach is used assuming repeat symmetry for the protrusions. The loading on the unit cell is applied by the application of boundary conditions. These boundary conditions are derived from a finite element model for the whole joint, designated the global model. The local stresses found from the global model at the critical regions are extracted. This system of stresses is then applied to the unit cell models containing a single protrusion. The flowchart in Figure 3 summarises the steps required for these analyses.

Figure 3 Flowchart showing the steps in the analyses

From experimental observations, the crack is initiated within the composite near the double step end and propagates from the first several protrusions on the step, indicated by the red circle in Figure 1. Simulations of the global model, loaded to the experimentally observed stress at first failure, 116MPa, were carried out. The stresses near the double step end were extracted; these stresses are the axial stress, S11, the transverse stress, S22, and the shear stress, S12. These stresses were then used to load the model containing an individual protrusion, which is the unit cell model. The stresses were loaded separately onto the unit cell models since different boundary conditions were required for each direction of loading. The results from the different loads were subsequently combined using Python scripting.

The optimisation is considered as the reduction in critical stress concentrations around the protrusions. The most critical stresses are the transverse peel stress and the shear stress; these stresses are the cause of delamination in composite laminates. Observation of the experimental results indicated that this failure mechanism caused the joint failure.

The geometric parameters varied in the simulations were:

- Protrusion density; varied between the measured density (D) and half that density (D/2.0)
- Protrusion shape; parallel shape or hill shape
- Protrusion angle; varied between -30° and $+30^\circ$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The global model has been analysed for the measured density of protrusions (D) and half the density (D/2.0). The extracted stresses in the critical region are found to be dependent on the protrusion density. The lower density of protrusions leads to a more gradual change in material properties between the titanium and composite laminate thus lower stress concentrations. The values of the extracted stresses are shown in Table 1.

	Axial Stress S11 (MPa)	Peel Stress S22 (MPa)	Shear Stress S12 (MPa)
D	105.7	0.4695	12.04
D/2.0	103.7	0.3818	12.55

Table 1 Values of stress extracted from the global model

The unit cell models were loaded with the values of stress shown in Table 1. For a given model, separate simulations for the three stress values using the appropriate boundary conditions were carried out. The results from the three simulations were subsequently combined to produce the overall results.

The experiments show that cracks initiate in the composite, and propagate along the top of the protrusions. Stress contour results for the composite region at the top of the protrusion have been studied; an example is shown in Figure 4. These are contour results of stress components: the axial stress S11, the peel stress S22, and the shear stress S12 for hill shape protrusions with angle -10° and measured density D. The maximum stresses all occur around the top of the protrusions indicating that composite failure is expected to occur in this region. The protrusion is oriented leaning towards the titanium end of the joint. The maximum tensile values of axial and peel stress are on the edge of the protrusion nearer the composite end of the joint.

Figure 4 Stress contours in composite above the protrusion

The maximum stress levels in the composite for the different models have been extracted and are shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5 Values of maximum stress for different models: (a) axial stress, S11; (b) peel stress, S22; (c) shear stress, S12

The results in Figure 5 show reduction in maximum stress for the reduced density of protrusions for all stresses and all angles. The normal stresses imposed on these models were lower (see Table 1) but the reduction in values of maximum stress are far greater than the reduction in imposed stress. The shear stress imposed for the lower density was higher but the resulting shear stress is lower. This reduction in stress concentration may arise from the greater distance between protrusions for the lower density such that the stress distributions around neighbouring protrusions do not interact.

The effect of the shape of the protrusions can be examined for the measured density, D. Values of axial stress, S11, are lowest for vertical parallel protrusions, but lowest at angles of $+10^\circ$ or -10° for the hill shape protrusions. Axial stress is not expected to cause failure in these joints; however, the results in Figure 5a indicate that this stress may become critical for protrusion angles greater than $+20^\circ$ or -20° .

Values of peel stress, S22, are generally smaller for negative angles with the exception of the value for -30° for the parallel shape protrusions. This high value for high negative angle may arise from interaction between the top of the protrusion and the titanium adherend below. This indicates that high protrusion angles may not be favourable. Since peel stress is the stress direction most likely to cause failure, the results in Figure 5b indicate that negative peel angles are more favourable.

The direction of the angle does not affect the value of maximum shear stress; the graphs are symmetrical. The lowest value of shear stress, S12, is for the vertical protrusion. The increase in stress values for higher angles is far lower for the hill shape protrusion compared with the parallel shape protrusion.

The most favourable shape of protrusion has been shown to be the hill shape. The more favourable angle direction is negative, towards the titanium end of the joint. This conclusion arises from the variability of the peel stress. However, the angle should not be too high since this causes large increase in the axial stress which may become critical and may cause increase in values of stress from interactions between the top of the protrusion and the adherend.

CONCLUSIONS

This novel bonding method for combining metal and composite laminates shows great promise. Finite Element Analysis is a powerful tool to optimise the geometry of the protrusions. The simulations have shown that reduction in protrusion density, so that interactions between stress distributions between neighbouring protrusions are avoided, reduces stress concentrations. The optimum shape of the protrusion is hill shape and the optimum angle is about -20° , slanted towards the titanium end of the joint.

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